

HERMENEUTICAL OPENING OF PRINCIPLES AND JUDICIALIZATION OF POLITICS: THE RISKS OF JUDICIAL ACTIVISM IN BRAZIL

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19370530

Thiallyta Hanna Alves Assis

*Master's student in the Postgraduate Program in Law at the Federal University of Ceará
(UFC), Email: thialitahanna@gmail.com*

Vanessa Monteiro Lima

*Doctoral student in the Postgraduate Program in Law at the Federal University of Ceará
(UFC); Email: vanessamonteirolima27@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the influence exerted by hermeneutic openness, wrapped up in the Theory of Principles, in the context of judicial decisionism, and its interrelationship with the Judicialization of Politics. The aim is to understand how this hermeneutic openness has influenced the formation of a decisionism based on the personal morality of the judge. Therefore, the aim was to define the norm as a genre, made up of two species: rules and principles, seeking to understand the actions of the judge in difficult cases in the face of hermeneutic openness. Methodologically, an inductive approach was adopted, based on academic works, containing the interdisciplinarity between Law and Philosophy based on the relationship between legal institutions and their limitations between powers and freedom. Finally, it was found that the maxim of proportionality, which primarily limits arbitrary decisions, has come to be used in Brazilian jurisprudence as a legitimizer of decisions contrary to current rules.

Keywords: Proportionality . Hermeneutics Openness . Judicialization of Politics .

INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to analyze the interrelation between the hermeneutical openness brought about by principle-based norms and the phenomenon of the judicialization of politics, particularly the consequence of judicial activism. It seeks to demonstrate how this greater discretion in normative interpretation has contributed to the emergence of activism, giving

judges the legitimacy to judge according to their political and moral opinions, without commitment to established law.

In contemporary times, Law is permeated by profound social and moral values. This penetration began in the post-World War II period, as a consequence of the crisis in existing normative control models. Political absenteeism in the other branches of government led to the expansion of the judiciary's functions, granting it more powers and increasing the demand for legal recourse.

This work will begin with an explanation of the fundamental concepts of the Theory of Principles, namely the most up-to-date concept of norm and the subdivision of the genus into two species, rules and principles, and the peculiarities of each subspecies in their definition and practical application. Having presented the basic concept of principle, the epistemological openness present in the application of such norms and their relevance in resolving difficult cases will be analyzed.

Next, a reflection is proposed on the principle of proportionality, which emerges as a criterion for resolving difficult cases when there is a conflict between fundamental principles or rights. The role that the rule of proportionality plays in Brazilian jurisprudence will be discussed, particularly in decisions that reject pre-existing solutions for that specific case.

This study also examines the phenomenon of the judicialization of politics, defining its facets and presenting its consequences for the democratic rule of law, notably the consequence of activism. It concludes with a discussion of the increased power of the judiciary resulting from the rise of social values in law and the hermeneutical openness caused by these factors, as well as by the inefficiency of the system of checks and balances in the face of the growth of the judiciary.

This research aims to establish an interrelation between the hermeneutical openness of law and the rise of the Judiciary, showing how the increased decision-making capacity of judges has legitimized a decisionism based on the judge's political and moral opinions. This makes the judge the personification of justice, legitimizing them to decide according to their own values, without commitment to established law.

Methodologically, an inductive approach is adopted, based on academic works, encompassing the interdisciplinarity between Law and Philosophy from the perspective of the relationship between legal institutions and their limitations between powers and freedom. Furthermore, the study of this theme is essential because it falls within a context of the leading role of the Judiciary, whose activity also unfolds in the judicial process geared towards the magistrate's decision.

Thus, this predominantly exploratory research is grounded in the fields of Constitutional Law and General Legal Theory, more precisely in the parameters for conceptualizing abstract legal terms and the general theory of fundamental rights. The research questions of the object of study are: 1) What are the difficulties in applying the rule of proportionality in Brazilian jurisprudence? 2) Does the leading role of the Judiciary highlight the difficulties brought about by the epistemological openness of law? The hypothesis is that the application of the rule of proportionality, without due depth, can produce judicial decisions based more on the feelings of judges than on established norms.

The development of the study is structured in five sections. Excluding the introduction and conclusion, there is the second section entitled "On the Hermeneutical Opening of Principles." In it, a theoretical summary of legal norms is presented, especially the approach of Dworkin and Alexy (Apud Neves, 2013). Following this, the impasses of hard cases are addressed, based on the complexity of the theoretical constitution of rules and principles, especially when invoked in practical approaches.

Thus, based on the dilemmas faced in hard cases, the third section begins, entitled "The Case of the Proportionality Principle," whose content focuses on the theoretical approach to the rules of proportionality involved in the interpretation and application of law. In addition, considerations are presented regarding the misuse of proportionality in Brazilian jurisprudence.

Furthermore, the fourth section, "The Judicialization of Politics and the Problem of Activism," addresses the dangers of the interference of proportionality rules in legal practice, considering Judicial Activism a problem to be overcome in light of the epistemological openness of law and the leading role of the judiciary. Finally, it was found that the principle of proportionality, primarily intended to limit arbitrary decisions, has come to be used in Brazilian jurisprudence to legitimize decisions contrary to existing rules.

FROM THE HERMENEUTIC OPENING OF PRINCIPLES

The post-World War II period proved to have brought about structural changes in the social sciences, particularly in legal sciences, given the chaotic state that prevailed during that time, which demonstrated the inadequacy of existing normative control mechanisms. In this sense, the rigid definition of a norm could not withstand the rise of values in contemporary society. As Soares (2016) teaches, the crisis in modernity opened the way for the emergence of diverse theoretical approaches in legal science, giving rise to postmodern law.

Furthermore, in postmodernity, law has come to be seen as a plural system, offering new cognitive frameworks for its study, marked by the valorization of social factors and the rapprochement between law and philosophy, permeated by reflections on reality. Moreover, the supremacy of the Constitution as the fundamental hermeneutical norm of the State has caused a revolution in legal science, making it a political, historical, philosophical, and sociological point of reference. In this sense, after the welfare state, the Constitution has acquired material elements, assuming a link with politics (Albuquerque, 2011), and creating a system focused on the realization of constitutionally recognized rights.

In this new system, legal norms are seen as a genus encompassing two species: rules and principles. This phenomenon, in addition to conferring greater legal relevance on values, placing them on the same level as rules, has generated an epistemological opening in law, expanding the interpretative role of the judge. In this sense, the concept of norm coined by Friedrich Müller (cited in Alexy, 2015) has prevailed in contemporary times, in which there is no identity between the norm and the text in force, since the legal norm surpasses the text, being more than what is read in it.

Thus, the true concept of a legal norm is determined by social reality, with the normative text being merely the *program of the norm* (Alexy, 2015). This definition, in itself, already produces an epistemological opening, as it advocates a practical construction of law, attributing a truly creative role to the judge. Initially, the Judiciary was conceived as a body responsible for merely pronouncing the already established norm, that is, without an executive function. However, with the advent of the Second World War, in Western democracies, it assumed the role of a true guarantor of fundamental rights, acting both in the control of the other powers and intervening in the democratic process of their realization (Carvalho Filho, 2014).

Thus, the nuances between principles and rules are not a settled issue in global and national legal doctrine. While for Dworkin and Alexy it is a qualitative separation of a logical nature, in Brazilian doctrine such nuances develop through the degree of generality, abstraction, or fundamentality (Silva, 2003). The debate between rules and principles is initially introduced in Brazilian doctrine through the so-called general principles of law, of a holistic nature and representative of fundamental ideas of the legal order.

However, it should be noted that this sense of principles does not correspond to the existing articulation between constitutional rules and principles, since, according to this line of thought, principles have a lower hierarchy than rules, only playing a supplementary role in filling gaps (Neves, 2013). Later, a differentiation criterion based on generality is adopted, in which principles would be more general than rules; however, this criterion proves flawed and

without practical consequences, given the existence of constitutional rules that carry semantic imprecisions (Neves, 2013). Currently, the prevailing idea in the theory of principles is that the distinction between principle and norm is qualitative, so that rules and principles are seen and studied as norms with distinct structures, different forms of application, and their own solutions to normative conflicts (Lima, 2012).

For this distinction, rules can be considered as laws applicable to a predetermined set of situations foreseen in the norm. Furthermore, they do not allow partial application of their precepts, only admitting the complete and uniform submission of the presented content. That is, a valid rule is applicable while an invalid rule is not applicable (Silva, 2003). Thus, for example, if a case of type A qualifies for the application of rule B, this rule will be applied to it in its entirety, being applicable whenever cases of type A occur, until another norm modifies or revokes it. In this way, rules are applied according to the logic of "all or nothing," using the criteria of hierarchy, temporality, and specialty in the conflict between rules, either in isolation or in combination, to decide, in that specific case, which rule is valid, and therefore, applicable to it (Soares, 2016).

Principles, conceptualized by Robert Alexy (2015) as optimization mandates, have their application tied to the specific case, being applied to a greater or lesser degree depending on the peculiarities. The clash between principles is resolved in the dimension of weight, through weighing, applying the norm to the greatest degree of realization possible in that factual situation (Neves, 2013). In other words, when the norm is a principle, its application stems from the specificities of the concrete case, and not from the genre to which it belongs; a principle does not become invalid simply because it has not been used in a given concrete case, so that it can, without prejudice to the legal order, be applied to another case of the same genre, to a greater or lesser degree than in the previous one, given the specificities.

Given the above, the complexity involved in conceptualizing principles, as well as classifying this category at the normative level, becomes evident. This contention generates direct consequences in the practical application of law, especially in resolving difficult cases, traditionally called *hard cases*, which are not resolved by simply subsuming the fact to the norm.

The dilemma of deciding hard cases.

In the words of Streck (2008), difficult cases depend in their genesis on the judge's capacity for interpretation, granting them discretion from their identification to their resolution,

since the criteria for resolving them are not found in the application itself, as occurs in *easy cases*, but rather in the theory of discourse, requiring prior justification. In this sense, new argumentative methods emerge as a way to resolve *hard cases* and maintain the full functioning of the legal system:

In this brave new world of constitutional interpretation, several new legal categories have been developed or refined, including: i) the recognition of normativity in principles and their qualitative distinction from rules; ii) the addressing of the phenomenon of collisions between constitutional norms, both principles and fundamental rights; iii) balancing as a technique for resolving these conflicts, overcoming the limitations of purely presumptive reasoning; and iv) the rehabilitation of legal argumentation, of practical reason, as a basis for legitimizing judicial decisions that are not based on the traditional logic of the separation of powers, as they involve a degree of judicial creativity (Barroso, 2028, p. 5).

Given this, the debate focuses on existing *hard cases* where rules and principles collide, in which the traditional criteria of prevalence of the valid rule and weighing are not capable of resolving the problem. Thus, rules and principles are distinct categories of norms, which have their own application and are guided by specific argumentation parameters. Therefore, they demand different argumentative burdens, directly impacting judicial activity. Thus, in the face of a collision between a principle and a rule, the choice of one or the other may generate antagonistic consequences. (Lima, 2012).

The most accurate response to the conflict between a rule and a principle is that the rule, being restrictive, should prevail over the principle, which is a mandate for optimization that can be applied to a greater or lesser degree depending on the case, restricting its scope of optimization (Lima, 2012). In other words, for those who think this way, the rule in that situation acts as a limiter of the principle, and should be applied if it is not contrary to the legal order, given that it follows the maxim of "all or nothing," so that its non-application would consequently represent its invalidity, while the principle admits gradation, so that its eventual restriction in that specific case would not imply its extinction.

This solution, at first glance, appears compatible with the theory of principles, turning what was once called a *hard case* into a simple apparent conflict of norms, which has a pre-molded solution in which the rule always prevails. Although the rule is the result of a legislative choice made between two principles (Streck, 2008), it proves insufficient in cases where its application develops in an unjust manner and is incompatible with social reality (Silva, 2009).

The main consequence of the solution proposed above lies in the realm of constitutional review, since no restriction on a constitutional principle, even one that establishes a

fundamental right, however burdensome, could be considered unconstitutional (Lima 2012). In light of the above, it can be described that, in routine cases, the rule proves to be an appropriate legislative choice for a specific case. However, in challenging cases, which present the unstructured complexity of the environment, principles prove to be more suitable for providing a peaceful and just solution, preserving constitutionality.

In this sense, the rule arises to domesticate the principle and make the decision of the case easier, not to annul it, so that in the end a rule will always be applied, whether it is the existing one or a new one formed from the conflicting principle (Neves, 2013). However, it is not possible to surgically separate, based on a theory of argumentation, what is an easy case from what is a difficult case. This is because, depending on the social and legal experiences of the judge, the solution to the dispute may seem obvious or present itself as complex (Streck, 2008), generating an epistemological openness, given the lack of objective criteria capable of guiding the application or not of subsumption by the magistrate.

Thus, difficult cases depend on the judge's interpretive capacity, granting them discretion from identification to resolution, since the criteria for resolving them are not found in the application itself, as in *easy cases*, but in the theory of discourse, requiring prior justification. Dworkin (cited in Neves 2012) points to Judge Hercules as the ideal magistrate, capable of identifying a difficult case and resolving it based on the set of applicable constitutional principles. However, this assertion raises questions, because how will this judge know which principles are actually applicable? Furthermore, is there really only one decision considered correct for resolving the case? Legal practice tends to show that this is not the case (Neves, 2012).

Dworkin's thinking, moral perspectives and principles are inherent to the concept of law, even if they are not supported by the legal text, and should always guide decision-making. However, despite the best intentions of this theory, it morally conceals a judicial decisionism (Maus, 2016). In contrast to the idea of preserving rules, in Brazilian law there is a phenomenon dubbed by Lênio Streck (2012) of *panprincipiologism*, in which, to highlight an important right, or to give special attention to a fact, it is called a principle, with the simple purpose of indicating its prevalence when confronted with other values considered less important.

In short, a principle is extracted daily from each constitutional decision (Streck, 2012), in a form of conceptual pollution, where even those who invoke the norm as a principle do not know for sure the meaning they are invoking. The term "principle" is sometimes a synonym for constitutional norm, or a mere argumentation technique. The real intention of those who argue in this way is only to justify their opinions as legitimate for the specific case, even if these are

contrary to the current normative text. Therefore, in the absence of objective parameters for defining and classifying principles, the meanings of such terms are emptied, leaving them subject to subjectivism, in which these values lose their original role as means of optimizing fundamental rights, to serve as instruments for justifying facts already decided, giving political and personal decisions the appearance of legitimacy.

THE CASE OF THE MAXIMUM OF PROPORTIONALITY

Based on the previous conclusions, there are special cases in which the techniques of subsumption and measurement are not sufficient to resolve the specific case, a factor that endows the *hard case* with an undesirable and dangerous discretion, because, without any criteria to frame the legal argumentation, establishing limits for it, the judge can decide arbitrarily, and even unjustly, threatening the Democratic Rule of Law and legal certainty.

As already highlighted, theories of legal argumentation return to law in post-positivism, making the norm a construction obtained in the confrontation between the normative text and the concrete case. However, legal certainty is also an idea pursued in this new generation of legal science, so that mathematical rigor is still present in contemporary legal theories, making it inappropriate to leave the solution of the case to the argumentative discretion of the judge (Peixoto, 2015).

Thus, the proportionality test is created with the objective of preventing abuses caused by the disproportionate restriction of principles, avoiding unnecessary suppressions. In the theory of principles, it is used for the maintenance and review of state acts, serving as a form of control over them. Therefore, proportionality seeks to prevent the achievement of a specific objective from implying the restriction of fundamental rights and other constitutionally protected interests; it is a restriction on restrictions (Lima, 2012).

Furthermore, the principle of proportionality, which originated in Germany as an argumentation technique, quickly gained global proportions, even in countries that adopt the *common law tradition*, such as England, becoming, with exaggeration, a global model of constitutional law (Lima, 2020). In Brazil, it was no different; in the last 20 years, mentions of proportionality have been intensely present in Brazilian doctrine, jurisprudence, and legislative production. The most expressive symbol of the principle of proportionality in Brazil is its inclusion in the 2015 Code of Civil Procedure, as a guiding element, directing the application of law alongside principles of constitutional order (Lima, 2020).

However, despite the widespread use of proportionality in the country, Brazilian jurisprudence sometimes makes mistakes when defining German proportionality, which is sometimes confused with English reasonableness, as if they were synonyms (Silva, 2002). Thus, although there are controversies regarding its classification as a rule, maxim, or principle, it is certain that proportionality is an argumentative structure used to justify decisions on the maintenance or revision of acts, especially state acts, preventing fundamental rights and guarantees from being suppressed in the pursuit of an objective.

The rule of proportionality serves for the interpretation and application of law and is commonly divided into three sub-rules, namely, adequacy, necessity, and proportionality in the strict sense, sometimes ignored in the jurisprudence of the SUPREME FEDERAL COURT, which in several situations does not even mention them and, when it does, limits itself to defining them in summarized concepts (Silva, 2002). At first glance, the order presented may seem merely enumerative, without depending on a specific sequence; however, it represents a succession, adequacy must necessarily precede necessity, which precedes proportionality in the strict sense (Silva, 2002).

The first step to be taken to determine whether a measure is in fact proportionate consists of analyzing whether the solution employed in the case under discussion promotes the achievement of a legitimate objective, which may be either a fundamental right or a constitutionally protected interest. If, on the other hand, the measure taken does not contribute in any way to the realization of this right or interest, it will be inadequate and consequently disproportionate (Lima, 2012).

The correction of an action and judicial intervention in a specific case must demonstrate the inadequacy of the measure adopted (Peixoto, 2015). Therefore, although intervention may still be justified under the other sub-rules (necessity and proportionality in the strict sense), the analysis of adequacy, even if independent, is mandatory before analyzing the others, as these have a subsidiary relationship. The analysis of necessity involves comparing the presented alternative with other measures capable of achieving the same objective, with the same intensity, but which affect the fundamental rights of those involved in the dispute less. Thus, before examining proportionality, it is necessary to identify and catalog which fundamental rights are involved in the dispute or may be affected by it (Silva, 2002).

In the meantime, necessity, as well as the general idea of proportionality, is a complex reasoning structure stemming from the idea of optimizing principles, since, if there are two or more means of promoting an end principle, the one that least affects the conflicting principle should be chosen (Bustamante, 2008). Finally, for a measure to be considered proportional, it

must also pass a final criterion, in addition to adequacy and necessity, namely proportionality in the strict sense, which consists of weighing the intensity of the restriction that the measure entails against the importance of realizing the fundamental right or constitutional interest that underlies the measure (Silva, 2002).

Basically, the final stage of the proportionality test seeks to prevent state measures, even if considered adequate and necessary, from restricting constitutional interests in a disorderly manner, beyond what their interest is capable of justifying. However, it is not a prohibition of intense limitations, but an examination that relates the intensity of the damage caused by the affected interests and rights with the benefits promoted from the fostered interests and rights (Lima, 2012).

The misuse of proportionality in Brazilian jurisprudence.

In Brazil, the use of proportionality has been heavily criticized due to consequences that are the opposite of those desired by the theory. It is constantly used as a rhetorical device that distorts its argumentative requirements and structure in order to give judicial decisions a sophisticated theoretical veneer and legitimize individual positions.

In light of this, it is noteworthy that the *New Rhetoric*, whose exponent was Chaim Perelman (cited in Peixoto, 2015) turned the focus of Law towards the study of legal argumentation, shedding light on important findings. An important conclusion of the new rhetoric is that legal reasoning is oriented towards persuasion and not towards presenting truths (Peixoto, 2015). Thus, the mention of one theory or another in a judicial decision does not mean that it was actually applied in that specific case; it only means that the judge in question used it as an argumentative resource to justify their thesis, functioning as an *argument from authority*.

In light of the above, it can be seen that Brazil is currently experiencing what Lênio described. Streck (2012) calls this the *positivation of values*, given that, customarily, the judiciary tends to announce new constitutional principles, as many as necessary to resolve difficult cases, or to correct uncertainties in language. For this jurisprudence, all types of principles are treated as paradigms of the democratic rule of law, behaving as philosopher's stones capable of attributing legitimacy to any decision.

In light of this, analyzing the jurisprudence of the SUPREME FEDERAL COURT, it is observed that, although the court uses the rule of proportionality with relative regularity, it is invoked in a superficial way, without delving into its complexity, composed of sub-rules, as developed in German jurisprudence. Thus, proportionality is treated as an argumentative and

rhetorical resource, a *topoi*, to be used when one wants to overturn a certain decision or norm (Silva, 2002).

Thus, when the court resorts to the rule of proportionality to invalidate an act of the other branches of government, outside of the three hypotheses in which it is applicable – a decision that does not promote a legitimate interest, a decision that is more restrictive than equally effective alternatives, or a decision of unjustified intensity – the body that performs the constitutional review ceases to be a review instance, responsible for verifying the compatibility of the normative act with the constitution, and begins to act as a decision-making instance, which replaces the measure adopted by the state bodies with the one it believes to be more convenient (Lima, 2020).

Thus, the use of optimizing weighting by the judiciary implies the negation of rules and the departure from constitutional principles in the name of the virtue of justice. However, this principle of justice, used in decisions, can assume various interpretations, which serves to accommodate concrete and particular interests, to the detriment of the normative force of the Constitution (Neves, 2013).

Silva (2002) argues that, in the decisions of the SUPREME FEDERAL COURT, the examination of proportionality is composed of premises of dubious foundation, which makes them fragile from an external point of view, thus generating problems. This is because the recourse to the rule of proportionality is not always justified in the Court's decisions, which do not have in their judgments an in-depth reflection on whether the constitution actually adopts the rule of proportionality.

In this sense, one can see the prostitution of important legal concepts, such as balancing and the dignity of the human person, which, due to their excessive use in every case, become banal, an event that ends up simplifying constitutional law and promoting distortions in the real meaning of the concepts used (Neves, 2013). As is frequently observed, mentions of proportionality in the decisions of the SUPREME FEDERAL COURT aim to convince public opinion or peers at any cost to support their opinion, choosing reasons and lines of argument strategically. (Lima, 2020).

Thus, it is noted that proportionality in Brazil serves political reasons more as an argument to reject undesirable measures than legal reasons, such as protecting fundamental rights. Therefore, the concept used here is distorted, representing a mistaken importation of a foreign theory.

The judicialization of politics and the problem of activism.

Given the increased role of the Judiciary in realizing constitutional rights, prompted by the epistemological openness that principle-based norms have brought to law, several questions arise regarding the power the body possesses to decide on public policies and the limits of its powers in realizing the fundamental rights demanded. The debate regarding the Judicialization of Politics and Judicial Activism falls within these questions.

Given the need to materialize constitutional norms, the role of magistrates in the control of constitutionality has become fundamental. Through the resolution of specific/individual cases, the judiciary assumes a leading role (Albuquerque, 2011). Adding this leading role of the judiciary to the inefficiency of the other branches of government in implementing public policies, a scenario of crisis in political representation emerges.

In the context of political crisis, a strong judiciary appears as a guarantee for new democratic arrangements, defending a democratic and rigid constitution with a catalog of supreme fundamental rights threatened by parliamentary majorities. This results in a new way of applying the law, with increased judicial activity and the predominance of this power in political and subjective decisions. Jurisdiction becomes a weapon in the struggle for power (Barbosa and Koziki, 2012).

Thus, reflecting on the realization of fundamental rights in the current constitutional model must take into account the fact that jurisdictional powers are limited, so that the court cannot, in its implementing action, encroach upon the competence of the other powers (Legislative and Executive). Furthermore, the judiciary must respect the rules established by the Democratic Rule of Law, otherwise a democratic regime will erode into a *Juristocracy* (Streck, 2016).

Thus, debating the realization of fundamental rights requires due reflection on politics, judicial decision-making, and the mutual influences they exert. Indeed, the interference of judicial protagonism in the realization of rights and the execution of public policies is undeniable, acting sometimes as a hero, sometimes as a villain. Given the above, there are two phenomena that study the relationship between politics and the Judiciary: the Judicialization of Politics and the Politicization of Justice, the latter understood in this article as synonymous with Judicial Activism.

Although they are treated as synonyms, there are differences between the two phenomena mentioned above. Judicialization is a phenomenon specific to democracies, and can occur to a greater or lesser degree depending on the political structure of the state. Given the

central role that law occupies in contemporary constitutionalism, a more pronounced role of the judiciary in the realization of fundamental rights is normal and desirable, so that occasionally the judiciary will be called upon to decide, through rationality, on political decisions that supposedly violate rights (Streck , 2016).

Given the political crisis in the Brazilian state, the discrediting of the political class is causing the phenomenon of the Judicialization of Politics, defined as the increasing use of the justice system in cases where the legislative and/or executive branches are perceived as flawed, negligent, or unsatisfactory. This requires the Judiciary to take a position on various political issues (Couto and Oliveira, 2019).

Thus, the judicialization of politics prompts the Judiciary to decide on issues of broad political and social impact, dealing with matters previously discussed in the parliamentary and executive spheres. The judiciary is sometimes called upon to act as a protector of minority rights, whose rights are violated and/or who find themselves excluded from the political process, and in this situation they resort to the jurisdiction to fill the gaps left by the other branches of government (Fonseca and Couto, 2018).

It is noteworthy that there are no hermetic boundaries or limits established by the constitution for this political action of the judiciary. Thus, despite the clear role of the magistrate in the realization of social rights, even constitutionally attributed to it, the limits of judicial interpretation are unknown (Albuquerque, 2011), which creates a danger for the system of separation of powers.

This intense interference by the Judiciary in political matters, such as the separation of powers, the implementation of public policies and fundamental rights, can represent a risk to democracy, given that it confers upon a non-elected power, and therefore not subject to democratic control, the capacity to interfere in agendas reserved for democratic agents, minimizing the system of checks and balances (Couto and Oliveira, 2019).

In this way, it becomes clear that judicialization is a circumstantial phenomenon, as it arises depending on political instability and the inadequate functioning of institutions, so that the greater the possibility of discussing, within the jurisdictional sphere, the adequacy/inadequacy of governmental action to constitutional dictates, the greater the degree of judicialization (Streck , 2016).

Thus, it can be seen that judicialization has a dual character, because on one hand it gives voice to minorities and enables debates that, whether due to ignorance or negligence on the part of other branches of government, do not find space in other spheres, allowing the realization of marginalized fundamental rights and the implementation of public policies. On

the other hand, this same phenomenon mitigates the democratic character of politics, giving an unelected power the strength to implement executive measures and to create the law that it itself applies, which weakens the system of checks and balances.

Furthermore, parallel to the Judicialization of Politics, there is the phenomenon of the Politicization of Justice or Judicial Activism, understood as the use of the justice system in decisions of an ideological nature, politically controversial, which escape the expected neutrality of such actors in the Democratic Rule of Law, assuming a political-partisan character, with political agendas specific to the judicial actors (Couto and Oliveira, 2019).

Thus, judicial activism is always harmful to the democratic system, since it stems from the subjectivism and personal views of judges and courts, using the public machinery to defend private and particular agendas. Furthermore, it is linked to judicialization, insofar as it arises from the responses offered to its process. Therefore, in activist decisions, the will of the judge replaces political debate, whether with revolutionary intentions or to maintain the *status quo* (Streck , 2016).

Currently, the justice of a decision is linked to the personality of the judge, shaped by ethical training, which acts as an indication of the existence of a just value system. Thus, Supreme Court justices are seen as "prophets" or even "gods of Olympus," exercising a true role as the *superego of society* (Maus, 2016). The justice and legitimacy of a decision are more closely tied to the personality of the judge than to the law.

Therefore, an activist stance leads to judicial populism, as well as offenses against fundamental rights and the democratic state. Given that they are subject only to internal control, with a low rate of accountability for their actions, judges and prosecutors are given the freedom to pursue their own values, which are not always aligned with legal and/or constitutional precepts.

It is understood that while the first is a product of the exercise of control mechanisms (*checks*) (*and balances*) in a democratic context, the second results precisely from the lack or ineffectiveness of such instruments; while the Judicialization of Politics can represent a recourse for citizens and collectives in defense of their rights, preventing abuses of power or omission by rulers, the Politicization of Justice can signify a threat to individual and collective rights as a result of excesses committed by actors in the justice system. In a way, this phenomenon evokes the classic dilemma of who controls the controllers (Couto and Oliveira, 2019, pp. 143-144).

Thus, however beneficial and/or progressive the activist decision may initially appear, granting rights, it can cause harm to the legal system, as it does not originate from the democratic system and does not respect the rules of the constitutional game, exceeding the

powers conferred upon the Judiciary. Therefore, this decision is not subject to state control and depends on the personal judgment of the judge, who, at their discretion, can decide to grant or deny rights according to their political agenda, without any commitment to the law.

Through judicial activism, the Judiciary moves from a controlled position, with institutional functions assigned and regulated by the constitutional text, to a controlling position, dictating the course of political agendas, and choosing which social groups will have their rights ensured, and which groups will have their freedoms curtailed, acting as a true dictator of justice, which abandons the abstraction of the norm to become embodied in the person of the magistrate.

It is also worth noting that the growth of the Judiciary in the 20th century did not represent merely an objective expansion of its functions, through an increase in its capacity for interpretation or the consolidation of judicial control over the legislature. This expansion was accompanied by an almost religious veneration of the judiciary by the population, such that any criticism of constitutional jurisdiction is seen as anti-democratic (Maus, 2016). Thus, reversing political decisions made by activist judicial bodies presents itself as a Herculean task, since such decisions are only subject to internal control, by appealing to higher instances within the same body.

The Legislative and Executive branches find themselves confined, bound by what has been decided, requiring complex political maneuvers, such as changing the texts of legal and constitutional norms (Couto and Oliveira, 2019). Furthermore, another problem to be highlighted is the lack of legal universality that activism causes, given that it involves personal opinions disguised in a legal guise, which for this very reason are not repeatable for all similar cases.

Streck (2016) teaches, a fundamental question that classifies a decision as activist is whether the decision is repeatable for similar cases. If the answer is negative, there is strong evidence that one is facing an activist decision. Therefore, the measure of activism transforms jurisprudence into a lottery, in which it is impossible to predict who is entitled to the right, given that the decision is determined to a greater degree by the judge's feelings than by established norms.

Therefore, the defense of fundamental rights must confront the politicization of justice, given that the latter, in addition to restricting democratic discussion, which in itself constitutes a fundamental right, also uses epistemological openness to condition the granting of rights to a lottery, offering rights to the same extent that it stifles them, in the name of political agendas.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article sought to explain how the hermeneutical openness of principles, combined with the phenomenon of judicialization, ultimately led to the emergence of judicial activism. Furthermore, it also aimed to highlight the existence of a decision-making process based on the judge's personal opinions, without commitment to established law and legal certainty.

As demonstrated, the concept of norms as social constructs has, in itself, expanded the magistrate's interpretative margin, leading them to abandon interpretation based on the mere subsumption of facts to norms and assume a creative role in interpreting the dispute. In this sense, the concept of *principles as optimization mandates*, subject to weighing, adds to this discretion, justifying the substitution of rules in specific cases in *hard cases*.

The lack of an objective criterion for differentiating between easy and difficult cases has contributed to the phenomenon of activism, as it leaves the judge's discretion to choose when to use subsumption and when to disregard the rules in order to employ a *sui generis solution*, developed for that specific case.

Furthermore, the principle of proportionality, originally developed to serve as a restriction on discretion in the protection of fundamental rights, has proven flawed in Brazilian jurisprudence, serving only as a mere argumentative tool to legitimize personal decisions that find no justification in current law.

Furthermore, the judicialization of politics has led to the judiciary increasingly deciding on social issues related to the implementation of public policies and fundamental rights, acting as a true *superego of society*, responsible for dictating the morals and customs of the population.

Therefore, the view of the Magistrate as a champion of justice, responsible for the final word in resolving specific cases, coupled with the lack of efficient means of controlling jurisdiction, has weakened the democratic process, delegitimizing political actors and representing a risk to the legal order and the system of separation of powers.

REFERENCES

ALBUQUERQUE, Felipe Braga. **LAW AND POLITICS: Assumptions for the analysis of political issues by the judiciary in light of the democratic principle**. 2011. Doctoral Thesis. University of Fortaleza - UNIFOR.

ALEXY, Robert. **Theory of Fundamental Rights**. São Paulo: Malheiros, 2015.

BARBOZA, Estefânia Maria de Queiroz; KOZICKI, Katya. Judicialization of Politics and Judicial Control of Public Policies. **Revista Direito GV** , v. 8, p. 059-085, 2012

DOS SANTOS CARVALHO FILHO, José . Between the guardian of promises and the superego of society: limits and possibilities of constitutional jurisdiction in Brazil. **Revista de informação legislativa** , v. 51, n. 202, p. 159-179, 2014

FONSECA, Lorena; COUTO, Felipe Fróes. Judicialization of Politics and Judicial Activism: a necessary differentiation . **Electronic Journal of Law and Politics** , v. 13, n. 2, p. 824-854, 2018.

LIMA, Rafael Bellem . Proportionality in the Supreme Court: an idea out of place. **REI-Revista Estudos Institucionais** , v. 6, n. 1, p. 184-206, 2020.

LIMA, Rafael Scavone Bellem de. **Optimization of principles, separation of powers and legal certainty: The conflict between principle and rule** . 2012. Doctoral thesis. University of São Paulo.

MAUS, Ingeborg. The Judiciary as the Superego of Society. Translated from German by Martonio MB Lima and Paulo A. de M. Albuquerque. 2016. researchgate.net.

NEVES, Marcelo, **Between Hydra and Hercules** : Constitutional Principles and Rules as a Paradoxical Difference in the Legal System. São Paulo: WMF Martins Fontes Ltda, 2013.

PEIXOTO, Fabiano Hartmann. **Judicial decision-making in the Brazilian Supreme Federal Court and the application of Robert Alexy's theory of principles** : balancing as a strategy of legal argumentation. 2015.

SILVA, Virgílio Afonso da. Fundamental rights: essential content, restrictions and effectiveness. São Paulo: Malheiros, 2009. _ . **The proportional and the reasonable** . Revista dos Tribunais, v. 798, p. 23-50, 2002.

SOARES, Ricardo Maurício Freire. **Elements of general theory of law** . 4th ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2016.

STRECK, Lênio Luiz. From pan-principle-ism to the insufficient conception of principle. **Revista de Informação Legislativa** . Brasília, v. 49, 2012.

STRECK, Lenio Luiz. Between Activism and the Judicialization of Politics : The Difficult Realization of the Fundamental Right to a Constitutionally Adequate Judicial Decision. **Space Legal Journal of Law** , vol. 17, no. 3, p. 721-732, 2016.

STRECK, Lênio Luiz. Hermeneutics and Constitution: The consequences of the undue division between easy cases and hard cases in law. **Fundamental Rights and Justice** , São Paulo, n. 2, p. 192-213, Jan./Mar. 2008.